

Polarographic Determination of Thallium (I) and Vanadium(V) in Mutual Presence and Compositions of Thallous Vanadates

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A rapid and accurate polarographic method for the determination of small amounts of thallium(I) and vanadium(V) in presence of each other has been developed, involving even 0.5 mg. of thallium (I) in presence of higher amounts of vanadium (V) and *vice versa*. Employing this method, compositions of different thallous vanadates, obtained by the interaction of Tl_2SO_4 and alkali vanadates (ortho-, pyro-, and meta-), have also been investigated.

Carnelley¹ prepared a series of thallous vanadates and particularly mentioned that by mixing solutions of Tl_2SO_4 and Na_3VO_4 , thallous pyrovanadate was precipitated instead of the expected orthovanadate. There is, however, no reference in the literature to the electrometric study of thallous vanadates. The purpose of the present investigation is to study suitable conditions under which thallium (I) and vanadium (V) can be determined simultaneously by polarographic method and to confirm the compositions of thallous vanadates, already arrived at from amperometric study². Heretofore an acidic supporting electrolyte consisting of 0.1M- H_2SO_4 , in which the precipitates were soluble, had been employed and recommended for the simultaneous polarographic determination of thallium(I) and vanadium(V) in solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

AnalaR (B.D.H.) reagents of Tl_2SO_4 , V_2O_5 , H_2SO_4 , NaOH, and gelatin were used in preparing their solutions in air-free conductivity water.

A manual polarograph with d. m. c. having $m=1.96$ mg./sec., $t=4.42$ sec., and $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.006$ mg. $^{2/3} t^{1/6}$ (in 0.1M- H_2SO_4 at $E_{d.c.} = -1.0$ v vs. S.C.E.) was used in conjunction with S.C.E. connected to the cell by low-resistance salt bridge. The cell solution was deaerated by bubbling pure hydrogen. Necessary correction for residual current was applied in determining all diffusion current data. A 0.005% gelatin solution was used as maximum suppressor.

Effect of the Variation of Concentration on the Diffusion Currents of Thallium (I) and Vanadium (V).—The polarographic behaviour of Tl^+ in 0.1M- H_2SO_4 as the supporting electrolyte containing 0.005% gelatin was studied. The linearity of Tl^+ ion concentration with its wave height was tested. A series of polarograms of solutions containing different concentrations of Tl^+ ions was registered. The diffusion currents at various concentrations were

determined; the values of i_d/C were calculated and found constant. Plot of i_d vs. C provided a straight line, indicating that i_d varied linearly with concentrations of Tl^+ ions.

The polarography of vanadium (v) in acidio media is well known³. The diffusion currents due to reduction of V^{5+} to V^{4+} at zero applied potential were found to vary linearly with concentrations of vanadium (v) ions. Plot of i_d vs. C for this also yields a straight line, suggesting the proportionality of i_d with C . The results are tabulated below.

TABLE I

Effect of varying concentrations of Tl^+ and V^{5+} ions on diffusion currents.

Tl_2SO_4 .	i_d^* .	i_d/C .	V_2O_5 .	i_d .	i_d/C .
2.00 mM	15.125 μA	7.562	1.00 mM	6.975 μA	6.975
1.33	10.100	7.576	0.66	4.560	6.910
1.00	7.530	7.530	0.50	3.486	6.976
0.83	6.270	7.564	0.40	2.820	7.050
0.40	3.030	7.575	0.20	1.385	6.975
0.20	1.510	7.550	0.10	0.694	6.940
0.00	0.756	7.560	..	..	..

* After correction for i_d .

A fairly appreciable difference in the reduction potentials of vanadium (v) (zero volt) and thallium (I) (-0.48 vvs. S.C.E) ions as well as the linearity of diffusion currents with their concentrations, provide a good means for the determination of both (Tl^+ and V^{5+}) in presence of each other, and hence the compositions of thalious vanadates.

Determination of Tl^+ and V^{5+} in Mutual Presence.—Several mixtures containing known amounts of thallium (I) and vanadium (v) in presence of 0.1M- H_2SO_4 and 0.005% gelatin were prepared. Using standard addition method⁴, the amounts of Tl^+ and V^{5+} ions in these mixtures were determined. For the determination of vanadium contents, an exactly known volume of the solution was taken in the cell each time and the initial diffusion current was measured. From the increase in diffusion current after adding a known volume of the standard solution, the amount of vanadium (v) was calculated. For the determination of Tl^+ ion concentrations, separate solutions were used. The polarograms were drawn before and after addition of the standard solution and similarly from the increase in diffusion currents, the thalious ion concentrations were calculated. Table II illustrates the results and the accuracy of the method.

TABLE II

Simultaneous determination of Tl^+ and V^{5+} in different mixtures.

Mix. No.	Present (mg.).		Found (mg.).		Error (mg.).	
	$Tl(I)$.	$V(V)$.	$Tl(I)$.	$V(V)$.	$Tl(I)$.	$V(V)$.
1	0.5396	4.0690	..	4.0650	..	0.0040
2	1.6350	2.5478	1.6850	2.5370	0.0500	0.0108
3	16.3500	0.2028	16.5100	0.2698	0.1600	0.0070
4	10.2190	1.0190	10.3010	1.0123	0.0820	0.0067
5	0.5396	0.1272	0.5232	0.1330	0.0164	0.0058
6	0.8160	0.2028	0.7960	0.2090	0.0260	0.0062
7	10.2190	2.5478	10.1500	2.5226	0.0690	0.0252
8	16.3500	4.0690	16.1000	4.0650	0.2500	0.0040

2. Saxena and Mittal, this *Journal*, 1964, 41, 125.

Determination of the Compositions of Thallous Vanadates.—The precipitates of different thallous vanadates were obtained by the interaction of thallous sulphate and solutions of alkali ortho-, pyro-, and meta-vanadates. Sodium pyro- and meta-vanadates were prepared by adding requisite quantities of HNO_3 to a boiling solution of Na orthovanadate, which was prepared by dissolving a known amount of V_2O_5 in boiling NaOH solution of the required strength. After filtration and washing several times with distilled water, the precipitates were dried in an oven at $110\text{--}20^\circ$ to a constant weight. An accurately weighed quantity of each precipitate was dissolved in H_2SO_4 (0.1M) containing 0.005% gelatin. Using standard addition method, the amounts of Tl^+ and V^{5+} present in each solution were determined and the ratio of $\text{Tl}_2\text{O}:\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ for each compound was calculated. The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Ppt. obtained by mixing.	Ppt. dissolved. in H_2SO_4 .	Amounts found.		Ratio $\text{Tl}_2\text{O}:\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$.	Probable formula.
		Tl (t).	V_2O_5 .		
Tl_2SO_4 & $3\text{Na}_2\text{O}.\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ (ortho)	100.00 mg.	79.51 mg.	17.306 mg.	2.04 : 1	$\text{Tl}_4\text{V}_8\text{O}_7$ (pyro)
Tl_2SO_4 & $2\text{Na}_2\text{O}.\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ (pyro)	94.20	74.66	16.800	2.00 : 1	$\text{Tl}_4\text{V}_8\text{O}_7$ (pyro)
Tl_2SO_4 & $\text{Na}_2\text{O}.\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ (meta)	100.00	67.49	29.990	1.001 : 1	$\text{Tl}_2\text{O}.\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ or 2TlVO_3 (meta)

DISCUSSION

Table II shows that thallium (I) and vanadium (V) can be determined simultaneously in presence of H_2SO_4 (0.1M) as the supporting electrolyte and 0.005% gelatin polarographically. The accuracy and reproducibility of the results have been found to be excellent. It is observed that higher amounts of vanadium (V) interfere in the determination of small amounts of thallium (I) and should be avoided because the large diffusion currents due to vanadium (V) mask the diffusion currents of thallium (I). Also the reducible ions having half-wave potentials between 0.0 to -07 v (vs. S.C.E.) should be absent.

Employing the present polarographic method, the molecular ratios of $\text{Tl}_2\text{O}:\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ in different thallous vanadates obtained from Tl_2SO_4 and alkali ortho-, pyro-, and meta-vanadates have been determined. In the case of the precipitates formed by thallous salt with sodium ortho- and pyro-vanadates, the ratio of $\text{Tl}_2\text{O}:\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ was found to be 2:1 in each case, corresponding to the formation of only one thallous pyrovanadate of the composition $\text{Tl}_4\text{V}_8\text{O}_7$. It was striking to note that the thallous orthovanadate was not obtained by the interaction of thallous salt and sodium orthovanadate, which is in agreement with the observations of Carnelley¹. With sodium metavanadate, however, thallium (I) formed thallous metavanadate, TlVO_3 . The results on the compositions of these vanadates are in full agreement with those obtained from amperometric study².

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